

ARTISTIC WORLD OF IRIS MURDOCH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554796>

Karimova Nozima

JSPI, 2nd year master's student

Abstract: *This article is dedicated to the artistic world of A. Murdoch. In Murdoch's work, the narrative tradition of English prose of the XIX century proves its continuity and productivity. Jane Austen, Charles Dickens, Henry James are no less close to this artist than James Joyce and Virginia Woolf. For more than thirty years of her work, her novel has undergone stylistic and aesthetic complication. It originated as a novel of ideas and remains so to this day. But in the complex of the writer's ideas, ethical ones were increasingly put forward in the first place. Despite the many abstractions and limitations, mainly of a social nature, it is the consistent search for goodness, a positive hero, true moral values in the cruel and complex modern world that distinguishes Murdoch and puts her in a special, high place among the philosophical novelists of England.*

Key words: *a positive hero, true moral values, novel, irony, artistic world,*

Murdoch's irony is a fusion of the sublime, beautiful, sad, creepy and funny, taking many-sided and diverse forms and extending to all spheres of human experience and existence. Such irony really does not allow comedy or tragedy in its "pure" form, but turns the picture of existence arising from the pen of the writer into a tragicomedy. According to Murdoch, the unnatural unity of the incongruous has its source not so much the imperfections of human nature and social structures, all going back to the same chaos, as the absolute, supreme paradox of being – the inseparability of life and death. For Murdoch, the mere fact that death is, and not just is, but inevitability and immutability, gives existence a qualitatively new dimension, changes the very perception of life.

The presence of death in the artistic world created by Iris Murdoch is pervasive – from the clinically immaculately written extinction of life ("Bruno's Dream", 1969) to the numerous *momento mori* waiting for the reader on the pages of her books: "... the loneliness of the sea and that special feeling, now realized as a feeling of death, which it seemed to always be in I was inspired" ("The sea, the sea"). To say that the taste of death gives the sharpness of life in Murdoch's books would not be quite accurate, and that's not the point: it gives a special intensity and purity to the very experience of life with all its injustices and even abominations, tames chaos and somehow fills being with meaning. It is ambivalent and dialectical, it is an experience, and it is impossible to understand whether the obsession with the "dumb horror of mortal flesh, stupid, soulless, irreversible" ("The Black Prince") results in a piercing feeling of "the fragility of the human body, its fragility, fragility, its complete dependence on extraneous causes" ("Sea, Sea"), or, on the contrary, awareness of the fragility and frailty of the flesh generates the fear of death.

In Murdoch's work, the narrative tradition of English prose of the XIX century proves its continuity and productivity. Jane Austen, Charles Dickens, Henry James are no

less close to this artist than James Joyce and Virginia Woolf. No less close, but no less far from it. And this is the paradox of the Murdoch style, its unsolved nature. Murdoch turned to the past of literature, having passed the school of modern artistic culture and philosophy. She did not write in the manner of Joyce, but without the revolutionary influence exerted by this writer on the literature of the XX century, the Murdoch phenomenon would hardly have arisen. In her worldview, in the power of thinking and writing, an extraordinary, original, unlike anyone else, Murdoch is the heir to two traditions – the English prose of the XIX century from Austen to Hardy and the intellectual prose of our time from Wolfe to Sartre. Moreover, both traditions have been creatively reinterpreted.

Therefore, it is so difficult to attribute Murdoch's work to any one artistic direction, to close the framework of a rigid definition. It is no coincidence that a number of Soviet researchers call her novels, especially of the last decade, realistic, their opponents strongly define her manner as modernist. There are also those who attribute ideological and stylistic easiness to Murdoch's work, which are supposedly a tribute to the tastes of the mass reader. Mutating, evolving, highlighting their new sides, her favorite types appear on the pages of Murdoch's novels – merciless "magicians", idle contemplators of the "human comedy", artists who have lost themselves and just ordinary people of the intellectual environment. And new, as always, mind-blowing plots, unraveling, leave the feeling that the reader is offered options for the same endless novel. It seems that the answers to these questions, which Murdoch formulates, are also missing. It seems that the last word of this conversation about life and death, about the aesthetic and moral essence of art, about truth and goodness, is about to be said, carried out by decades of reflection, but reservations and doubts follow, and the unchanging irony and complete encryption of the author's position reinforce the feeling of shakiness of almost final conclusions.

And yet it is not in this incompleteness of thought that the dominant of the worldview is Murdoch. For more than thirty years of her work, her novel has undergone stylistic and aesthetic complication. It originated as a novel of ideas and remains so to this day. But in the complex of the writer's ideas, ethical ones were increasingly put forward in the first place. Despite the many abstractions and limitations, mainly of a social nature, it is the consistent search for goodness, a positive hero, true moral values in the cruel and complex modern world that distinguishes Murdoch and puts her in a special, high place among the philosophical novelists of England.

Murdoch has her own saints, or at least candidates for such – Hugo Belfounder from the first novel, James Temper Pace in *The Bell* (1958) or Brenden Craddock (Henry and Cato, 1976). They also try to influence the course of events, they do it worse than the "wizards", but in essence the role of both those and others is purely nominal. It would seem that Misha Fox and Julius King are mysterious and omnipotent – they are not human hunters: people are caught on their own weaknesses and vices, and "wizards" Murdoch, like the evil spirits of M. Bulgakov, only manifest, catalyze this process. After all, in three famous novels of the 1970s, written by her in the first person ("*The Black Prince*", "*The Child of the Word*" and "*The Sea, the Sea*"), the narrators themselves act in

two roles simultaneously: "the wizard" and "the saint" - and are caught in the same way, they find themselves "under the net".

All this fits into the general chaos of life, which makes it cruel and unfair. "Life in general is unfair." – summed up in the novel "The Black Prince", which at the same time clarifies exactly why "Good does not triumph, and if it triumphed, it would not be good." And tears do not dry up, and the torments of the innocent and the sufferings of those who have experienced soul-crippling injustices are not forgotten. In another book, through the mouth of the hero, a guess is expressed that the confusion, disorder of life deprives it of a tragic beginning: "Everything in me is vulgarly confused – repentance, remorse, annoyance, violence, hatred. And there was no tragedy. Tragedy is in art. There are no tragedies in life" ("Child of the Word"). Where there is no place for tragedy, according to the logic of things, comedy should rule, but everything is not so simple for Murdoch: "Almost any story about our affairs is comical. We are infinitely funny in each other's eyes. Even the most beloved creature is funny to his admirer. The novel is a comic form... God, if he existed, would laugh at his creation. At the same time, it cannot be denied that life is ridiculous, meaningless, subject to the play of chance, that pain and the expectation of death rule over it. From this irony is born, our dangerous and inevitable weapon" ("The Black Prince").

REFERENCES:

1. Bellamy, (1977). An Interview with Iris Murdoch. Contemporary Literature, Madlton.
2. Blanchot, M. (1971). Le livre a venir. P. [63] Bradbury, M. (1973). Possibilities. Essays on the State of the Novel. Oxford. N.Y.
3. Byatt, A.S. (1980) Iris Murdoch. Lnd., 45.
4. Byatt, A.S. (1965). Degrees of Freedom: The Novels of Iris Murdoch, L.,
5. Conradi, P. (1986). Iris Murdoch: The Saint and The Artist. Lnd., 304.
6. Dipple, E. (1982). Iris Murdoch: Work for the Spirit. L.: Methuem & Co LTD, 3-280.